

Report
(Falco Project)

**Reducing ambiguity in 3D inversion of Magnetic and Gravity data
over a sector of Black River Group (BRG)**

For research project of
NSERC – Engage Grants

Bahman ABBASSI and Li zhen CHENG

Université of Québec in Abitibi-Témiscamingue
Institute of Mine and Environment
445, boul. de l'Université, Rouyn-Noranda (Québec) J9X 5E4
Téléphone : (819) 762-0971, poste 2558 Télécopieur : (819) 797-6672

Oct 2015

Preface

1. Introduction

Mineral exploration demands accessibility to deeper levels of upper crust since most outcropped orebodies are almost discovered on Earth. Therefore, the rate of discovery of large ore bodies are dropping fast and the subsequent expenses are growing. Expanding the exploration space is one handy solution to this demand and three dimensional inversion of geophysical data provides a fast and reliable resolution to address the problem.

Inversion of geophysical data enormously adds value to geological information about mineral deposits in three dimensions. The retrieved physical property model can help explorers to see lithological contacts, faults, chemical alterations and mineralization in more depth and detailed accuracy. This report, provides a broad study of magnetic and gravimetric physical property of rock samples in relation to their lithological, alteration and mineralization characteristics. These information subsequently were used to constrain the inverse modeling of magnetic and gravity data and interpret the recovered 3D distribution of physical properties based on the actual geological links.

This approach can help us to match geophysical 3D models to the available drillholes and then extend the model to the remote regions inaccessible regions to extend and predict geological properties.

Based on well established equations of potential field theory in geophysics, the geophysical responses can be calculated from distribution of physical properties within the Earth. This process is called Forward Modeling. The reverse mathematical process of recovering physical properties from a set of geophysical measured signals is called Inverse Modeling or Inversion (Blakely, 1996; Roy, 2008). In Figure 1 an example of forward and inverse modeling of magnetic data is presented. A buried magnetic body with significant magnetic susceptibility can produced a magnetic field anomaly at surface that can be measured with geophysical sensors. This natural process can be reproduced or forwardly modeled thanks to forward equations in mathematics of potential field theory. Therefore, through forward modeling, if we know the physical properties within the Earth, we can predict what we will measure with our geophysical sensors on top of the ground, on airplanes or even satellites. This physical process as only one straightforward solution. In other word, every forward calculation results in one single solution. The reverse procedure, that is usually called inverse problem, is the mathematical process of telling the subsurface physical property distribution by looking at the geophysical signal measured on the ground or plane. The solution of this inverse process is not unique. That means, an inverse calculation potentially

can produce several equivalent physical property models that can result in synthetic geophysical signals very well fitted on actual observations. This problem is usually called non-uniqueness in geophysical literature and it is a very important aspect of an inverse modeling (Blakely, 1996; Roy, 2008).

One solution for the non-uniqueness problem is constrained inversion based on drillhole physical property measurements. In unconstrained inversion, inverse calculations start from a homogeneous initial earth model. During the unconstrained inversion, this homogeneous physical property distribution gradually shift toward a distribution well-matched with surface observations. In constrained inversion, physical properties for several drillholes are known and based on this priory information the initial starting model is set as a more reliable starting point for forward subroutine and therefore the output of inversion will be closer to geological reality (Blakely, 1996; Roy, 2008).

Figure 1: vdfg

This strategy is crucially important for interpretation of geophysical data in less worked regions, specifically targeting deeper levels within upper crust. We performed several unconstrained inversion on gravity and magnetic data collected in the Abitibi greenstone belt (AGB). The study area is hosted within the Blake River Group (BRG) which is host to 33 volcanogenic massive sulphide (VMS) deposits, 17 inside of Québec province, including the world class Noranda Mine.

It is important to continue efforts to develop the mineral resources in mining areas in order to use the old infrastructure and avoid creating new tailings; Falco Resources is thus interested in the blank area to the west of the Flavrian pluton. According to few drill holes they knew that the stratigraphy near the surface is sub-horizontal (dipping 0 to 35 degree), where potentially host multiple horizons that are favorable for volcanogenic massive sulfide (VMS) type of mineralization. There are several gold showings in the area, and the litho-geochemical signature is

similar to that of host rocks of the Horne deposit. A reconstruction of the geology in three dimensions would allow Falco Resource to better understand the geological context and evaluate the mining development potential.

2. Geological Setting

The BGR is a well-known VMS deposit. The area is dominated by massive and brecciated rhyolite flows and andesitic lavas intruded by diorite and syenite intrusions and diabase and gabbro dikes (Figure 2). The study area is dominated by felsic intrusive rocks; about 50% of rhyolite and 30% of gabbro/diorite and syenite make up 7% of the study area. Several phases of deformation, folding and faulting are the causes of the current geology of GBR (Figure 3).

The database provided by Falco Resources included observations of more than 150 drillholes including lithological units, mineralization and alterations. The first step was selecting the drillholes with vertical lithological variation to measure their physical properties for constrained interpretation of geophysical data. These drill cores are located in Libraries of Évain and Destor near Rouyn-Noranda.

Figure 2: Blake River Group. VMS deposits and Flaws (Dion and Rhéaume, 2007).

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Study area. (a) Digital Elevation Model (DEM). (b) Surface geological map.

3. Drillhole Geological Data

Drillcore samples are collected by Falco Resources comprising valuable information about local geology and mineralization up to 1 km depth. We divided them in three parts (lithology, alteration and mineralization) and we used a three dimensional technique for spatial demonstration of them as it is followed in figures 4, 5 and 6.

Drillhole Data

Figure 4: Distribution of drillholes in three spatial projections.

Figure 5: Plan view of lithological, alteration and mineralization types. Major lithologies (Andesite, Rhyolite, Diorite and Syenite) are mostly epidotized, silicified and hematitized. Gold mineralization is occurred within Pyrite.

Figure 6: Cross section 5358220N looking north, showing the depth continuation of lithologies, alterations and mineralization.

4. Physical Properties

We measured magnetic susceptibility and bulk density of 214 drillcore samples in summer 2015 using Terraplus instruments. The histograms in figure 7 show frequency distribution of these physical properties within main lithologies. The average physical properties for Andesite, Diorite and Rhyolite samples are respectively $2.31 \text{ g/cm}^3 / 0.0132 \text{ SI}$, $2.41 \text{ g/cm}^3 / 0.0118 \text{ SI}$ and $2.13 \text{ g/cm}^3 / 0.0015 \text{ SI}$. Though in sense of physical properties each lithology hardly shows a distinct unimodal sharp distribution, but Rhyolite samples show mostly lower magnetic and density properties relative to Andesite and Diorite samples, making rhyolitic regions a good indicator of low magnetic anomaly in the regions. Very high magnetic anomalies are observed in Andesite rocks. Andesite and Rhyolite samples show wider range of variations in density values compared to Diorite samples. That suggest Gravity method can better identify the boundaries of diorite.

Figure 7: Histogram of physical properties measured in different dock units.

Geophysical Data

4.1. Inversion of Magnetic data

Inversion of magnetic data is performed by using Voxi Earth Modeling module implemented in Geosoft Oasis Montaj software (Geosoft Oasis Montaj, 2015). Unconstrained and constrained inversion results for upper part of the subsurface corresponding to the surface geology is overlain on geological boundaries in figure 8.

(a)

Unconstrained Inversion Elevation: 200m

(b)

**Constrained Inversion
Elevation: 200m**

Figure 8: Unconstrained (a) and constrained (b) inversion of magnetic data compared to the surface geology.

Constraining the results recovered more details about the actual lateral continuation of rhyolitic and dioritic body. The very high anomaly is probably a result of mixture of basalt, syenite and tonalite in eastern part.

Figure 9: Geological interpretation of constrained magnetic inversion (a). Unconstrained inversion is compared to the constrained one along the profile AB.

4.2. Inversion of Gravity data

Using the same platform in inversion of gravity data as in magnetic one (Geosoft Oasis Montaj, 2015), we improved the retrieved density 3D distribution by constraining the gravity inversion with drillhole density measurements. The central diorite body therefore is emerged on constrained inversion; something that is not very well seen on unconstrained model. Because distribution of density values within each lithology is more varying compared to magnetic properties, it is hard to identify and recover a lithological model out of gravity inversion results. What we can judge here is that low density anomalies are more or less related to rhyolitic body and higher densities are related to a mixture of diorite (mostly in central part), andesite and syenite.

(a)

**Unconstrained Inversion
Elevation: 0m**

(b)

Constrained Inversion
Elevation: 0m

Figure 10: Unconstrained (a) and constrained (b) inversion of gravity data compared to the surface geology.

Figure 11: Geological interpretation of constrained magnetic inversion (a). Unconstrained inversion is compared to the constrained one along the profile 5358300N Looking North. .

Resources

1. Blakely, R. J., 1996, Potential theory in gravity and magnetic applications, Cambridge University Press.
2. Dion, C., Rhéaume, P., 2007, Stratigraphie de la partie occidentale du Groupe de Blake River, Document publié par Géologie Québec.
3. Geosoft Oasis Montaj, 2015, Voxi Earth Modeling:
<http://www.geosoft.com/products/voxi-earth-modelling/overview>.
4. Roy, K.K., 2008, Potential Theory in Applied Geophysics, Springer.